

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 130

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 130

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 130:0 A Song of Ascents.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 130:1</p>
<p>Psa. 130:1 Out of the ^adepths I have cried to You, O LORD.</p>	<p>קָרָאתִיךָ יְהוָה : ² אֶדְנִי שָׁמְעָה בְּקוֹלִי תִתֵּינָה אַזְנוֹךָ קְשִׁבוֹת לְקוֹל תִּתְנוּנִי : ³ אִם-עֲוֹנוֹת תִּשְׁמַר-</p>
<p>² Lord, ^ahear my voice! Let ^bYour ears be attentive To the ^cvoice of my supplications.</p>	<p>יְהִי אֶדְנִי מִי יַעֲמֹד : ⁴ כִּי-עֲמֹד תִּסְלִיחָה לְמַעַן תִּזְכָּר : ⁵ קִנְיֹתֵי</p>
<p>³ If You, ¹LORD, should mark iniquities, O Lord, who could ^astand?</p>	<p>יְהוָה קִנְיֹתֶה נִפְשִׁי וְלֹדְבָרוֹ הִוְחַלְתִּי : ⁶ נִפְשִׁי לְאֶדְנִי מִשְׁמָרִים לְבִקֵּר שְׁמָרִים לְבִקֵּר : ⁷ יִתֵּל</p>
<p>⁴ But there is ^aforgiveness with You, That You may be ^bfeared.</p>	<p>יִשְׂרָאֵל אֶל-יְהוָה כִּי-עִם-יְהוָה תִּתְחַסֵּד וְתִרְבֶּה עַמּוֹ בְּדוֹת : ⁸ וְהוּא יִפְדֶּה אֶת-יִשְׂרָאֵל מִכָּל עֲוֹנוֹתָיו :</p>
<p>Psa. 130:5 I wait for the LORD, my ^asoul does wait, And ^{1b}in His word do I hope.</p>	
<p>⁶ My soul <i>waits</i> for the Lord More than the watchmen ^afor the morning; <i>Indeed, more than</i> the watchmen for the morning.</p>	
<p>⁷ O Israel, ^ahope in the LORD; For with the LORD there is ^blovingkindness, And with Him is ^cabundant redemption.</p>	
<p>⁸ And He will ^aredeem Israel From all his iniquities.</p>	

References

Psalm 130:1

^aPs 42:7; 69:2; Lam 3:55

Psalm 130:2

^aPs 64:1; 119:149

^b2 Chr 6:40; Neh 1:6, 11

^cPs 28:2; 140:6

Psalm 130:3

¹Heb *YAH*

^aPs 76:7; 143:2; Nah 1:6; Mal 3:2; Rev 6:17

Psalm 130:4

^aEx 34:7; Neh 9:17; Ps 86:5; Is 55:7; Dan 9:9

^b1 Kin 8:39, 40; Jer 33:8, 9

Psalm 130:5

¹Lit *for*

^aPs 27:14; 33:20; 40:1; 62:1, 5; Is 8:17; 26:8

^bPs 119:74, 81

Psalm 130:6

^aPs 63:6; 119:147

Psalm 130:7

^aPs 131:3

^bPs 86:5; 103:4

^cPs 111:9; Rom 3:24; Eph 1:7

Psalm 130:8

^aPs 103:3, 4; Luke 1:68; Titus 2:14

Targum

Psa. 130:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. From the depths I have called you, O LORD. ² O LORD, receive my prayer; may your ears be attentive to the sound of my prayer. ³ If you will take note of iniquities, O Yah, LORD, who will remain? ⁴ For there is forgiveness with you, so that you might be seen. ⁵ I have waited, O LORD; my soul has waited, and for his glory I have waited long. ⁶ My soul has waited long for the LORD, more than the watchmen on the morning watch who watch to offer the morning sacrifice. ⁷ Israel waits long for the LORD, for with the LORD is kindness, and with him is much redemption. ⁸ And he will redeem Israel from all his iniquities.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Songs of Ascent raised human spirits. The message of hope was never more important than during the Exile. The worst part of the Exile was when the people accepted the fact that their behavior caused the LORD to remove His protection from them and thus the Babylonian came to Judea to conquer it. This military move destroyed the sacred city of Jerusalem and the First Temple to the LORD.

Verse four

The English versions of this psalm like to say “You may be feared.” A proper translation is show reverence. The Psalmist says that one should indicate reverence to the LORD because only the LORD can forgive sins.

For with You there is forgiveness so that You may be revered.

Notes on the Psalm

Demonstrating reverence to the LORD is to obey the commandments and perform the mitzvot found in the Torah. It is actually a very simple formula. The Ten Commandments were written as a treaty. The LORD is the stronger partner. He said if Israel followed the Torah, then He would offer His protection. There came a point in time that the LORD could no longer accept the sin of the people. Therefore, he sent the Babylonians to destruct the Temple because it was no longer sanctified to the LORD. Too much pagan worship was occurring in the Temple. The LORD sent the Babylonians to destroy the Temple that was once dedicated to Him.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

